

Rizayeva Zohida

Boboyeva Dono

Teachers of the Technical College of Public Health

named after Abu Ali ibn Sino

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5972640>

BONE PAIN AND THEIR CAUSES

Annotation: *Pain in the bones is one of the most painful conditions that worries the elderly.*

Keywords: *bone, pain, causes, vitamins, symptom, blood, symptom.*

Bone pain is well known to many who have an acute form because it is a common symptom of broken bones or fractures. However, in various diseases, bone pain can progress to a chronic stage. Victims suffer from constant bone pain, often with significant deterioration in their mobility and daily life. In the worst case, the symptoms can be hidden from the cancer, so an emergency medical examination is recommended.

Detection of bone pain. Bone pain in the narrow sense should only be understood as pain recorded by nerves located in the bone marrow, periosteum, and bone matrix. However, it is often very difficult to differentiate complaints such as bone pain and joint pain or muscle pain. In particular, pain is also felt in the surrounding tissues, such as muscles, ligaments, and fascia, as part of a fracture because they are usually injured. Pain in the limbs as a general term includes pain in all muscles, joints, and bones.

Symptoms. Bone pain is generally perceived by those affected as dull, deep pain, which often increases significantly during stress. As a rule, it affects the bones above the knee, upper arm, ulna or tibia, but in theory the symptoms can manifest themselves in the entire skeletal system. Bone pain is often difficult to localize for victims. Bone pain can start suddenly or develop gradually over time and grow steadily. While some sufferers only suffer from bone pain when they are stressed, others also show appropriate symptoms at rest.

Because of the pain, patients adopt a protective state, which in turn leads to improper loading of joints, muscles, and ligaments. In this way, subsequent pain in the musculoskeletal system can occur as a result of bone pain. In addition to bone pain, a variety of accompanying symptoms may be observed for different causes of the complaint, which will then be explained in more detail in relation to the diseases of the relevant cause.

Causes of bone pain. Direct causes of bone pain include growing pains, fractures, bone diseases and metabolic disorders, ranging from metastatic malignant tumors. Bone pain should not be confused with joint pain, but it may be related to the exact same clinical appearance. For example, hip pain can be frequently observed in connection with osteomalacia, which in turn can lead to bone pain above the knee. The cause of bone diseases. Various bone diseases can lead to bone loss and related bone pain, with osteoporosis and osteomalacia (childhood rickets) being best known. Bone diseases such as aseptic bone necrosis, osteodystrophic deformities, and Engelmann syndrome are less common and therefore less well known.

Osteoporosis. Osteoporosis (loss of bones) is a symptom characterized by a decrease in bone density and an increase in sensitivity to broken bones. In general, older people are particularly affected because bone density naturally decreases with age. However, osteoporosis can be a side effect of other diseases, such as overactive thyroid or chronic polyarthritis. Some medications are also associated with an increased risk of osteoporosis. to be conditional Often, osteoporosis initially becomes insignificant, and eventually the first fractures appear as an insignificant cause. They are responsible for the sudden onset of bone pain as part of osteoporosis.

Osteomalacia. In osteomalacia (softening of the bone), the mineralization of the bone material is insufficient, which leads to an increase in the soft bone matrix in the bone structure. The disease is usually caused by vitamin D deficiency and / or calcium deficiency. Persistent dull bone pain is a hallmark of osteomalacia. The pain probably comes from the periosteum. Reptiles that can occur under osteomalacia can also cause significant pain in the affected bones. This type of floating fracture is more common, for example, on the inside of the femur. Patients with osteomalacia are prone to posture, which significantly increases the risk of musculoskeletal complaints. Softening of the bones in children is called rickets.

Aseptic bone necrosis. Aseptic bone necrosis (non-infectious bone infarction), where blood is supplied by local blood as a result of vascular occlusion and is remembered as a bone disease that causes bone pain. Then the bone tissue begins to die due to lack of oxygen, nutrients and minerals. Bone damage can be on a completely different level. From the imperceptible minimal loss of this substance to severe bone pain and serious irreparable injury associated with limited movement.

Osteodystrophic deformities. Bone pain can also be observed in the case of Paget's disease (Osteodystrophy deformities). This pathological change in the bones mainly affects the elderly and is characterized by inflammatory processes in the early stages, which are associated with an increase in the rate of bone regeneration and pain in the bones. The bones begin to thicken and deform. The pelvis, leg bones, and lumbar spine are increasingly affected. Changes in the bone can also be seen from the outside. The heat emitted by the skin is often significantly increased in the affected areas or the skin may feel overheated. Because changes in the bones sometimes put pressure on the nerve pathways, in terms of Paget's disease, complaints such as back and lumbar pain, sciatica, and muscle tension (e.g., neck tension) are common. can be observed.

Acromegaly. A rare form of bone disease that can be associated with bone pain is acromegaly, which is felt as an enlargement of the body called the end and acre (the part closest to the trunk of the body). It affects the feet and legs, fingers and hands, as well as parts of the nose, chin and face, such as the eyebrows or cheekbones. Acromegaly results from the overproduction of the growth hormone somatotropin, which is why it is medically called endocrine disease (hormone gland disease).The decisive factor in the development of the disease is that it begins before or after puberty. If the growing joints of the bones are not yet closed at the onset of the disease, the affected ones show an overall growth in the form of a giant growth instead of an extreme expansion of the body with corresponding changes in body proportions. If the growth plates are already closed at the onset of the disease, the

concentration of growth hormone somatotropin in acromegaly elsewhere leads to uncontrolled growth of articular cartilage and tissue structures. As a result, a remarkable shift in body proportions of affected people develops. In addition to bone pain, symptoms such as headache, fatigue, tiredness, increased sweating, and decreased sexual arousal may be observed as accompanying symptoms due to hormonal imbalance. Acromegaly also increases the risk of high blood pressure, diabetes and cardiovascular disease.

REFERENCES:

1. Y.K.Subulkina. Bolalarga tez tibbiy yordam. –T.: Abu Ali ibn Sino nomidagi tibbiyot nashriyoti, 1991.
- 2.S.S.Esonturdiyev, M.E.Qarshiboyeva. «Bolalar va o'smirlar gigiyenasi». –T.: Cho'lpon, 2002.
3. T.Umarova, A.Qayumova, M.Ibrohimova. «Hamshiralik ishi». –T.: Abu Ali ibn Sino nomidagi tibbiyot nashriyoti, 2003.